

Original software publication

RobustCheck: A Python package for black-box robustness assessment of image classifiers

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ARTICLE INFO

Dataset link: <https://github.com/andreiiilie1/RobustCheck>

Keywords:

Adversarial machine learning
Adversarial robustness
Computer vision
Black-box adversarial attack
Machine learning development tools

ABSTRACT

The robustness of computer vision models against adversarial attacks is a critical matter in machine learning that is often overlooked by researchers and developers. A contributing factor to this oversight is the complexity involved in assessing model robustness. This paper introduces **RobustCheck**, a Python package designed for evaluating the adversarial robustness of computer vision models. Utilizing black-box adversarial techniques, it allows for the assessment of model resilience without internal model access, reflecting real-world application constraints. **RobustCheck** is distinctive for its rapid integration into development workflows and its efficiency in robustness testing. The tool provides an essential resource for developers to enhance the security and reliability of computer vision systems.

Code metadata

Current code version	1.1.0
Permanent link to code/repository used for this code version	https://github.com/ElsevierSoftwareX/SOFTX-D-24-00187
Permanent link to Reproducible Capsule	https://codeocean.com/capsule/2082563/tree/v2
Legal Code License	MIT License
Code versioning system used	git
Software code languages, tools, and services used	Python, Pytest for testing, MLflow for experiment tracking, Sphinx for automatic documentation generation
Compilation requirements, operating environments & dependencies	Python ≥ 3.8.0, matplotlib ≥ 3.7.0, numpy ≥ 1.18.0, mlflow ≥ 1.2.0, tqdm ≥ 4.64.1 (note: all specified in <code>setup.py</code>)
If available Link to developer documentation/manual	https://andreiiilie1.github.io/RobustCheck
Support email for questions	cilie@fmi.unibuc.ro

1. Motivation and significance

1.1. Motivation

Computer vision systems have rapidly transitioned from novel innovations to essential components across diverse applications such as autonomous vehicles, medical diagnostics, and user authentication. Ensuring the reliability of these systems, particularly their robustness against adversarial attacks, is critical for user safety and data security. This reliability is paramount in real-world scenarios where anomalies, both natural and adversarially introduced, are common and can significantly impact performance.

Despite its importance, machine learning robustness has historically been overlooked, partly due to the complexity of evaluating it and the lack of accessible evaluation tools. This oversight perpetuates a cycle where the scarcity of evaluation tools stems from and contributes to the community's limited focus on robustness. Recent initiatives have begun to address this gap by developing tools for assessing the robustness of specific architectures [1,2].

To advance the state-of-the-art, we present **RobustCheck** [3], a user-friendly Python package designed to evaluate the adversarial robustness of computer vision classifiers through efficient evolutionary algorithms. Unlike previous tools, **RobustCheck** is architecture-agnostic

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.softx.2024.101831>

Received 22 March 2024; Received in revised form 12 July 2024; Accepted 15 July 2024

Available online 23 July 2024

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and integrates seamlessly into development and deployment workflows, facilitating broad adoption and enhancing the security posture of computer vision applications.

1.2. Related work

In our previous work [4] we introduced **AttackType.EvoBA**, one of the evolutionary algorithms that fuel **RobustCheck**, to efficiently assess the adversarial robustness of computer vision classifiers. This algorithm outperforms **SimBA** [5], a similarly purposed and widely used state-of-the-art adversarial attack, in terms of speed and requires fewer queries to produce adversarial perturbations of similar magnitude, offering a practical solution for rapid robustness evaluation. **RobustCheck** also provides support for running robustness evaluations using **SimBA**, broadening its range of adversarial techniques.

Compared with **ODE4ViTRobustness** [1], a similar tool which assesses the robustness of transformer-based models and requires internal model access, **RobustCheck** supports a black-box approach applicable to any architecture, aligning more closely with real-world application needs.

Another similar package, **Adversarial Robustness Toolbox** [6], provides support for assessing the robustness of machine learning models by using both black-box and white-box adversarial attacks. In comparison, **RobustCheck** specializes in black-box adversarial attacks, providing a lightweight way to run the more recent and efficient attack **AttackType.EvoBA**, which was shown in [4] to surpass in efficiency the former state-of-the-art attacks supported in **Adversarial Robustness Toolbox**, such as **SimBA** or Zeroth Order Optimisation (ZOO) attacks [7].

Our primary contribution is the introduction of **RobustCheck**, an open-source Python package designed to assess the adversarial robustness of various black-box computer vision classifiers. By employing evolutionary strategies that treat images as population individuals and mutate their pixels intelligently to deceive targeted models, **RobustCheck** offers more efficient and comprehensive robustness evaluations compared to similar tools. Integrating **RobustCheck** into development workflows is straightforward, as demonstrated by the code snippets in Section 2.3.

Section 3 illustrates how **RobustCheck** enables new research into enhancing neural network robustness through ensembling with gradient-boosted models. Furthermore, **RobustCheck** is used at **Bolt**,¹ Europe's largest super-app company for transportation and food delivery, to assess and enhance the robustness of the computer vision models used in micromobility. These include applications such as over-the-edge pedestrian or sidewalk detection from on-scooter cameras for safety purposes.

2. Software description

The methodology employed by **RobustCheck** is straightforward. It requires access to the inference method of black-box computer vision classifiers and a labeled dataset of images. **RobustCheck** uses black-box adversarial attacks to efficiently find adversarial perturbations for each image sample. It then generates and logs dataset statistics, including adversarial accuracy, average black-box query counts, and the average magnitudes (L0, L2 norms) of successful adversarial perturbations, helping developers understand the adversarial robustness of their models.

2.1. Software architecture

Fig. 1 presents a simplified overview of **RobustCheck**'s architecture, focusing on its core components and functionalities.

The primary user interface, **RobustnessCheck**, encapsulates the model under evaluation and a sample of labeled images, and builds **UntargetedAttack** implementations that execute the underlying adversarial attacks. The abstract class **UntargetedAttack** wraps the model and one labeled image, requiring implementations for `run_adversarial_attack()` to run the attack, and `is_perturbed()` to verify attack success.

EvoStrategy provides an interface for evolutionary strategies, encouraging open-source contributors to extend **RobustCheck** with new implementations that comply with the **UntargetedAttack** interface.

A useful implementation detail is that **EvoStrategyUniformUntargeted** includes a `clean_memory` flag to optimize memory usage. When enabled, it triggers `EvoStrategyUniformUntargeted.flush_memory()`, which clears the memory of all but the fittest individual per generation. This feature prevents memory usage spikes and helps support larger `generation_size` values.

The `utils` sub-module provides methods to save robustness check results, ensuring **RobustnessCheck** remains focused on its core functionalities. For example, `generate_mlflow_logs()` saves artifacts compatible with MLflow [8] servers, facilitating interactive visualization.

2.2. Software functionalities

Our package enables users to perform comprehensive adversarial robustness checks, generating a suite of robustness metrics for computer vision classifiers. The main functionality of **RobustCheck** is evaluating the adversarial robustness of black-box models against a labeled dataset of images. Developers can gauge the resilience of their models by determining how many correctly classified images can be adversarially perturbed under predefined conditions, such as black-box query limits and adversarial attack parameters. These conditions are flexible: users can either employ the default settings for immediate assessments or customize them based on heuristics we provide.

The robustness metrics produced by **RobustCheck** include the **adversarial accuracy** (percentage of images still classified correctly after **RobustCheck** attempted various perturbations), along with statistics of the black-box query counts and the magnitude of successful perturbations, measured by L0 (number of modified pixels) and L2 (Euclidean) norms. These equip practitioners with a clear understanding of their model's vulnerability to adversarial attacks, the computational effort required for such perturbations, and the severity of modifications needed to deceive the model. Access to the adversarially altered images is also provided, enabling further qualitative analysis.

Using these metrics, developers can take targeted actions to enhance model robustness, such as applying adversarial training [9] or distillation techniques [10]. **RobustCheck** provides a quantitative foundation for evaluating the impact of such improvements on adversarial resilience.

RobustCheck offers three ways to access its robustness metrics: displaying in a human-readable format on standard output, logging metrics and artifacts such as histograms on the disk, or logging metrics, artifacts, and perturbed images in an MLflow-compatible way.

2.3. Sample code snippets analysis

Our package simplifies the process of evaluating image classifier robustness through three distinct black-box adversarial attacks. The first adversarial attack, **AttackType.EVOBA**, leverages an evolutionary strategy to iteratively mutate images, selecting offspring most likely to evade correct classification as the basis for subsequent generations. The second, **AttackType.EPSGREEDY**, uses a variant of the classic Epsilon-Greedy strategy, commonly utilized in reinforcement learning [11]. This approach involves randomly altering pixels within specific groups chosen in advance, focusing on those groups that have

¹ <https://bolt.eu>

Fig. 1. Simplified architecture of RobustCheck.

shown to most significantly lower classification accuracy on average. Both strategies are designed to be straightforward yet effective, offering users practical tools for assessing and enhancing the adversarial robustness of their models. The third method, `AttackType.SIMBA`, is another simple and effective black-box attack that fits our rapid robustness evaluation framework. Using a greedy strategy, it iteratively attempts to perturb pixels at random by adding or subtracting a fixed amount of noise, only retaining modifications that reduce the image’s correct classification likelihood.

A robustness assessment requires the following:

- a model exposing a `.predict` method that outputs a class probability distribution,
- a labeled dataset of images `x_test`, `y_test`,
- the chosen attack²: `AttackType.EVOBA`, `AttackType.EPSGREEDY`, or `AttackType.SIMBA`,
- attack parameters via `attack_params` for the chosen method.

In practice, running a robustness assessment and obtaining the robustness metrics can be easily achieved by:

```

1 from robustcheck import RobustnessCheck
2 from robustcheck.types.AttackType import
  AttackType
3
4 model = load_model(...)
5 x_test, y_test = load_data(...)
6
7 rc = RobustnessCheck(
8     model=model,
9     x_test=x_test,
10    y_test=true_labels,
11    attack=AttackType.EVOBA,
12    attack_params={

```

² New users are recommended to start with `AttackType.EVOBA` for its faster execution and similar functional completeness compared to `AttackType.EPSGREEDY` and `AttackType.SIMBA`. `AttackType.EPSGREEDY` and `AttackType.SIMBA` require less adjustment of hyperparameters and can produce adversarial perturbations with fewer total black-box model queries, but generally take longer due to their iterative nature.

```

13         "generation_size": 30,
14         "
15         one_step_perturbation_pixel_count": 1,
16         "pixel_space_int_flag": True,
17         "pixel_space_min": 0,
18         "pixel_space_max": 255,
19         "steps": 100,
20         "verbose": False,
21     }
22 )
23 rc.run_robustness_check()
24 rc.print_robustness_stats()

```

A test using 1000 images from the CIFAR-100 dataset [12] with a classic VGG model [13]³ produced:

```

Robustness statistics – using AttackType.EVOBA
-----
Perturbed successfully 698/698 images
Adversarial accuracy: 0.0
Average query count: 207.13180515759313
Average l0 distance: 20.482808022922637
Average l2 distance per pixel: 0.0006218724202762773

Median query count: 151.0
Median l0 dist: 15.0

Max query count: 1891
Max l0 dist: 182
-----

```

In of the 1000 image sample, 698 were correctly classified before the robustness check. All 698 correctly classified images were successfully adversarially perturbed within 100 steps (`steps : 100`) using `AttackType.EVOBA`, with each step exploring 30 potential perturbations (`generation_size : 30`). Each perturbation modifies 1 random pixel (`one_step_perturbation_pixel_count : 1`) at a time. After the perturbations, none of the 1000 images were classified correctly, resulting in a 0% adversarial accuracy.

³ Used the implementation from [14].

Fig. 2. A histogram of the queries required to produce successful adversarial perturbations. This is one of the artifacts that both `utils.save_robustness_stats_artifacts()` and `utils.generate_mlflow_logs()` produce.

For best results, set `one_step_perturbation_pixel_count` to approximately 0.1% of an image’s total pixels. Increasing `generation_size` to 100–400 enhances speed but requires more queries. Refer to the original paper [4] for detailed guidance on tuning `AttackType.EVOBA`.

To log robustness artifacts, use the following code snippet:

```
1 from robustcheck.utils import
  save_robustness_stats_artifacts
2 save_robustness_stats_artifacts(rc,
  path_to_output)
```

This stores artifacts at `path_to_output`, including histograms of successful adversarial perturbation L0 and L2 norms (`l0_dists_histogram.png` and `l2_dists_histogram.png`), a histogram of query counts

(`queries_histogram.png` - Fig. 2), and a JSON file with both aggregated metrics and raw data (`robustness_stats.json`).

To generate MLflow-compatible artifacts, including all previously described metrics, artifacts, and perturbed images for quick qualitative assessment, use the following code snippet:

```
1 from robustcheck.utils import
  save_robustness_stats_artifacts
2 generate_mlflow_logs(rc, run_name,
  experiment_name, tracking_uri)
```

3. Illustrative examples

In our ongoing research, we enhance neural network robustness by combining them with gradient-boosted models, leveraging the inherent Lipschitz continuity of neural network layers [15]. This property ensures that input variations result in linearly bounded output changes, meaning adversarial perturbations accumulate across layers instead of causing large deviations in any single layer. We create a more robust stacked model by using an initial portion of a neural network as input to a gradient-boosted model.

We use **RobustCheck** to test our hypothesis that ensembles of gradient-boosted models and deep neural networks are more adversarially robust than deep neural networks alone. We compare the robustness of a VGG neural network, as described in Section 2.3, against a prefix of the same network ensembled with a final LightGBM [16]. Both models are trained on the CIFAR-100 training data and are validated using **RobustCheck** on a sample of 1000 test images. The results are presented in Table 1.

The ensemble model (**Stack**), which combines a neural network with a gradient-boosted model, consistently outperforms the standalone neural network (**NN**) in **adversarial accuracy**. The two attacks we

introduced, `AttackType.EVOBA` and `AttackType.EPSGREEDY`, are more effective and faster than `AttackType.SIMBA`, perturbing more images in less time. However, the improved robustness of **Stack** comes with a slight reduction in accuracy: **NN** achieve 70.48% accuracy on the CIFAR-100 test set, while **Stack** achieves 69.97%.

Comparing average query counts, distances, and iteration times across models with largely different adversarial accuracies can be problematic due to selection bias. This happens as robustness is influenced by both model design and the inherent characteristics of image samples [17]. When attacking robust models, fewer of the inherently more robust images are successfully perturbed, skewing the evaluation towards easier-to-perturb samples. For instance, when using `AttackType.EPSGREEDY` in our study, **NN** had a higher average query count (39.1) than **Stack** (36.2) for all perturbed images. Yet, when only considering images perturbed by both, the bias disappears, revealing average query counts of 35.4 for **NN** and 36.8 for **Stack** and reinforcing **Stack**’s superior robustness. Therefore, while these metrics indicate a measure of robustness, they require careful assessments. Adversarial accuracy, however, is unaffected by biases and serves as the most reliable robustness measure.

4. Impact

RobustCheck simplifies the evaluation of adversarial robustness for computer vision classifiers, simulating real-world scenarios where attackers only use API calls and do not have access to model internals. This tool addresses the often-overlooked aspect of adversarial robustness, aiming to shift the focus towards creating safer, more reliable models, especially as their use in critical areas increases.

Designed for developer convenience, **RobustCheck** provides quick and meaningful robustness metrics through efficient attacks. It integrates seamlessly into development workflows and CI/CD pipelines. This facilitates robustness testing and establishing baseline robustness criteria for automatic model deployment.

The `AttackType.EVOBA` attack, a key component of **RobustCheck**, is proven in our peer-reviewed research [4] to effectively assess the robustness of models such as ResNet-50 [18] or the classic LeNet [19] on standard datasets such as MNIST [20], CIFAR [12], or ImageNet [21]. We demonstrated that it matches the effectiveness of state-of-the-art black-box attacks while offering faster run times, thus enabling efficient robustness studies. Interestingly, our research found that simpler models and tasks tend to be more robust”.

The package is currently fueling our research into building more robust models by stacking components of deep learning models with gradient-boosted models such as LightGBM. Additionally, the package is used at Bolt, Europe’s first mobility super-app, to assess the robustness of computer vision models used in micromobility. These models include pavement classifiers that analyze images from scooter cameras to detect sidewalk riding, which is dangerous and prohibited in many cities.

The package has been downloaded almost 1000 times over slightly above one month since its release in late January 2024.⁴

5. Conclusions

In this work, we introduced **RobustCheck**, a Python package designed for the efficient and user-friendly assessment of adversarial robustness of computer vision models. **RobustCheck** is already enhancing our research into robust deep learning models and supporting industrial applications at Bolt, particularly for scooter-related vision models.

⁴ Download stats are tracked here: <https://www.pepy.tech/projects/robustcheck>.

Table 1

Comparison of robustness metrics for two models as output by *RobustCheck*. NN is a VGG neural network architecture, while Stack is an ensemble of a prefix of the same neural network and a gradient-boosted model.

Attack Type	Model	Adversarial accuracy	Average query count	Average L0 distance	Average L2 distance ($\times 10^{-4}$)	Seconds per iteration
EVOBA	NN	0.0%	204.5	20.3	6.1	1.4
	Stack	6.6%	255.0	25.0	6.2	2.6
EPS	NN	10.8%	39.1	49.4	8.6	1.8
	Stack	20.0%	36.2	38.4	7.5	1.2
SIMBA	NN	42.7%	73.5	36.6	1.8	4.7
	Stack	53.0%	73.6	22.6	1.4	3.34

While **RobustCheck** focuses on computer vision tasks, moving forward we plan to expand its capabilities to support text, audio, and video. Its adaptable design, based on evolutionary black-box strategies, will facilitate the integration of these modalities, providing a comprehensive suite for robustness assessment across various AI applications.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Andrei Ilie: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Alin Stefanescu:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

All code is open under MIT license <https://github.com/andreilie1/RobustCheck>.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used OpenAI's ChatGPT to enhance the manuscript's readability, identify and correct typographical errors, and refine the text for conciseness and clarity. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Acknowledgments

This research was partially supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101070455, project DYNABIC. We are grateful to Marius Popescu, professor at the University of Bucharest, who helped us develop `AttackType.EVOBA` as part of our original publication [4]. We would also like to thank Traian Delca and Amatia Lomax, senior data scientists at Bolt, who tested, provided feedback and adopted the **RobustCheck** package for their micromobility computer vision research.

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